

SARAS CALL h2020-ICT-2016-2017
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

SARAS

"Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon"

D 8.1 – Plan for Communication actions

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Dissemination Level	
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CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	
Int = Internal Working Document	

D8.1 – PLAN FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

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List of acronyms

PR = Press Releases

SEO = Search Engine Optimization

IDM = Innovation & Dissemination Manager

GDPR = General Data Protection Regulation

R-MIS = Robotic Minimally Invasive Surgery

T1 = Target 1 (General Public)

T2 = Target 2 (Healthcare Experts)

T3 = Target 3 (Researchers)

T4 = Target 4 (European Companies)

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Introduction

The aim of SARAS in the healthcare sector is to allow more hospitals in Europe to be able to afford the costs of a solo-surgery equipment and at the same time to reduce the cost per surgical operation. From the point of view of patients, SARAS aims to positively affect their safety and shorten waiting lists for prostatectomy and nephrectomy. In the Academic field, SARAS' working prototypes will boost the cooperation among research centers and open up new lines of research in the field of autonomous robotic systems as well as many others. Lastly, for what concerns Europe's economy, SARAS' purpose is to positively affect Europe's role in the robotic and image-guided surgery world market, providing a basis for new startups or existing manufacturers to grow and expand.

On the basis of these premises, the aim of the Work Package 8 "Communication and exploitation" is to promote SARAS and inform all stakeholders of its progress and developments; to demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges; to transfer knowledge and results to those best placed to exploit them; and to maximize the impact of research in the field, thus potentially allowing SARAS' outcomes to achieve a wider impact outside the original focus.

1.1 Purpose and structure of the document

As part of the European research network, SARAS should aim at demonstrating the ways in which research contributes to innovation, providing tangible benefits to society, contributing to competitiveness, generating results useful to the industry and the scientific community, and showing how its outcomes are relevant for social, clinical and technical reasons.

This document is primarily addressed to the project partners, and it is instrumental in Task 8.1 "Plan for Communication actions" and 8.2 "Plan for Exploitation and dissemination". Its structure is the following:

- SARAS identity definition and templates creation
- Market and Stakeholder analysis and definition
- Communication & Dissemination strategy
- Action plan

SARAS Brand Identity

The brand is the perceived image of the project and it is conceived to tell the audiences about SARAS' story, its growth, innovative elements and aims. A brand has a name, a personality, values, a character and a reputation: it is a promise and raises expectations. The identity of a project is vehiculated by visual tools used to represent the brand with consistency and coherence. All the digital and printed elements regarding Brand Identity, such as the logo, the website, templates, presentations and posters of the project, must have a coordinated image. In the following, the guidelines chosen for SARAS and their rationale are described.

1.2 Logo

The logo is the main visual element of the SARAS identity and allows someone to immediately recognize and recall the project. For these reasons, the concept of the project logo design is based on technological, innovative and health-related elements: a technological font, a sign that reminds a robotic arm and a chromatic palette that recalls the Hospital sector (see Figure 1). The logo is designed for contrasts to be bursting, amaze and attract attention. Its function is to hint at a project that breaks with the past and aspires to create something innovative.

1.2.1 The font

The font is Nasalization, an ultramodern sans serif typeface with a nod to the 1975 NASA logo. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration is the ultimate symbol of innovation, is the entity in charge of exploring new frontiers in the universe. By analogy SARAS explores new frontiers in the human body to develop the next-generation of surgical robotic systems.

1.2.2 The sign

The sign is the intuitive part of the logo, and the one of highest visual impact. It is made of two contrasting parts. In the foreground we have a stylized and simplified robotic arm to represent the technology of the project. By contrast, a geometrical figure lies in the background: the hexagon, a complex polygon with six equal sides and angles that convey the idea of rigour, complexity and symmetry.

1.2.3 The color palette

We chose two colours which, as the elements mentioned above, are in opposition to each other: *(i)* a tone of blue (Iris Blue), the typical colour used in Healthcare for its ability, attested by colour psychology, to normalize the heartbeat frequency and blood pressure, and to remove the sense of anxiety; *(ii)* and a tone of yellow (Ronchi), symbol of sunlight but also of knowledge and energy (see Figure 2). Again, combining two contrasting colours amounts to imposing a visual energy force on the composition.

Figure 1: SARAS Official Logo

Figure 2: SARAS Chromatic Palette

Moreover, different versions of the logo have been created for special needs: squared (see Figure 3) and favicon (see Figure 4) are contracted form for social media and avatar profile use; the negative (see Figure 5) and grey (see Figure 6) versions are necessary to ensure readability on white or coloured backgrounds.

Figure 3: Squared logo

Figure 4: Logo icon

Figure 5: Negative logo

Figure 6: Grey logo

1.3 Templates

A series of project templates (see Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9) have been created and will be further introduced to cover the partners' needs. In particular, project templates suitable for deliverables, factsheets, presentations, newsletters and press releases have been designed in order to be used by the project partners for internal and external dissemination. Every template created will be available on the SARAS website, under the section Downloads if public, or in the private project (See Deliverable D9.1 section 5.2), available only to Partners, if confidential or internal.

Figure 7: SARAS Deliverable Template

Figure 8: SARAS Poster Template

Figure 9: SARAS Presentation Template

1.4 Project presentation

A presentation is the best way to introduce the project to the desired audience and has the main function to inform about it. Different formats of printed or digital presentations exists, and the

typology depends on the usage, the audience and the distribution. We have produced a tri-fold brochure (see Figure 10) for external use, mainly to be easily distributed at events to advertise the project. The content will depend on the target audience, but some elements are mandatory for every presentation: the name and description of the project, its objective, the benefits/needs we aim to satisfy, the partners' logos and names and contact details. Brand identity must be respected for sake of consistency. The project logo and color palette need always to be present.

Figure 10: SARAS official Brochure

1.5 Poster

A project poster is a visual summary of the project presentation, designed to convey an immediate understanding of the project and its goals, mainly used in the research and academic sectors. Its main function is to attract the attention of the target audiences, especially at conferences, workshops and road shows.

Figure 11: Poster presented at the ERF2018

1.6 Impressum

In business, the *Impressum*¹ is a consistent legal term used primarily in Germanic countries, attached to a legally mandated statement of the ownership and authorship of a document. In these countries, the "Impressum" must be included in books, newspapers, magazines and website by law. An Impressum page on the web is similar to an "About us", "Company Info Pages", or "Terms & Conditions" pages.

In Italy, the *Legal Notes*² are mandatory on every website and must contain all the details of the physical or legal entity owner of the site.

The *Usage Right* is a form of protection of intellectual property granting the Consortium control on the dissemination process and the correct usage of the collaterals produced.

Because of the affinity of the arguments, we include all this information in one page called Impressum under the submenu Consortium. The usage rights are also included in the Downloads page of the project official website.

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/what-impressum-why-does-facebook-want-one-chris-bangs/>

² <https://www.plservizi.it/privacy-policy-note-legali-cookies-e-pec/>

1.6.1 Legal notes

The Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon (in short SARAS) project has no independent legal status but it is the result of work performed by a consortium of independent partners, temporarily created with the aim to perform research work under contract with the European Commission. The consortium retains collectively the rights to the information contained on this Web site.

The project started on 1 January 2018 and has a duration of 36 months.

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- No alterations may be made to pictorial content, with the exception of framing modifications to emphasize the central motive.
- The source must be quoted and two free reference copies must be sent to the above-mentioned address. Such usage is free of charge.

1.8 Project consortium

Name	Short name	Country
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI VERONA	UNIVR	Italy
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI MODENA E REGGIO EMILIA UNIMORE	UNIMORE	Italy
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	Italy
OSPEDALE SAN RAFFAELE SRL	OSR	Italy
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA	UPC	Spain
UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE	UNIVDUN	United Kingdom
OXFORD BROOKES UNIVERSITY	OBU	United Kingdom
MEDINEERING GMB	MEDIN	Germany
ACMIT GMBH	ACMIT	Austria

Table 1: Partners' list

General Disclaimer

The material or information provided on this Web site do not in any way represent views of the European Commission. Nor does it represent views of the individual partners.

The SARAS Project has made every reasonable effort to ensure that the content of this Web site is accurate and complete. However, the possibility of errors cannot be entirely ruled out. We do not give any warranty in respect of the timeliness, accuracy or completeness of material published on this Web site, and disclaim all liability for (material or non-material) loss or damage incurred by third parties arising from the use of content obtained from this Web site.

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Acknowledgements

The SARAS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 779813 (SARAS).

The SARAS project does not receive any external funding for the creation and maintenance of this site from advertisers or any other commercial interest.

1.9 Use of the EU logo

Beneficiaries of the EU's Horizon 2020 research have the obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This must be done, if possible and unless the Commission/Agency requests otherwise, in all communication, dissemination and IPR activities, as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results funded by the grant.

The following must be included in all communication and dissemination activities and displayed on all infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 779813 (SARAS).

High-resolution EU emblems are available here: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

Market segmentation

1.10 The process

A market segment is a homogeneous group of people with one or more common characteristics, needs or aims, grouped for marketing purposes by marketing professionals using various criteria. Each segment is unique and responds predictably to a marketing strategy. This is why marketers use segmentation when deciding a target market and approach each segment differently, after fully understanding the needs, lifestyles, interests, demographics, behavior and personality of the target consumer. The process of market segmentation is structured into a few steps, represented in the scheme below (see Figure 12: Market Segmentation process):

Figure 12: Market Segmentation process

1. The first step is a clear definition of the market of interest of the project.
2. The second step comprises: (i) the creation of market segments, which is the process of splitting the market into smaller groups with similar product needs or characteristics; (ii) the evaluation of these segments on a set of criteria and the construction of segment profiles.
3. The attractiveness of these segments are then evaluated, and one or more target market(s) are selected with the intention of heavily focusing the marketing activities towards this(these) group(s).
4. After market segment creation starts a strategic process that includes the development of a positioning strategy by identifying key benefits and relevant features for selected segments and building a “product” positioning in line with their perceptions.
5. After the strategy comes the plan: development and implementation of the marketing mix and performance review.

1.11 Market definition

The market of interest to SARAS is the robotic minimally invasive surgery (R-MIS) one; more in detail, the project focuses on innovations on active systems for manipulating robotic and laparoscopic tools localized in the European robotics industry.

1.12 Market segments

To create market segments and identify smaller groups with similar needs and characteristics we have split the market into macro areas based on the market definition; Robotics, Healthcare and Academia seemed to be the more appropriated ones.

We have then split each macro area into smaller groups of people, associations and companies; and differentiated them into experts, suppliers and users. The result is represented in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Splitting the market into macro areas

1.13 Target audiences

To evaluate the attractiveness of all these segments we have selected a small number of target markets in each area to restrict the number of groups to analyze to construct segment profiles. The result is presented in Figure 14:

Figure 14: Selecting Target audiences

Considering the huge number of audiences resulting from the initial selection, we decided to analyze them from a communication point of view and group them into macro target audiences based on common features such as: similar media channel used to stay informed, interest in the same contents and use of the same register, tone and way of communication.

From this analysis, the result can be grouped into four macro audiences:

- Patients, Geeks, Robotics’ Media and End users who want to know more about robotics. They have been included in the cluster *General Public* (T1) because they are all non-experts interested in the topics of robotics and healthcare, not involved in the use or the production of them and they all need the same registry and non-technical communication language.
- Hospitals and Clinical Centers, Surgeons and Medical Operators can be grouped into the cluster *Healthcare Experts* (T2), as they are all involved in the healthcare sector and the use of robotics for medical purpose; they adopt the same registry and technical communication language.
- In the Academia macro area researchers are the main target to address as part of the SARAS’ communication activities, which is why we have named this cluster *Researchers* (T3). All of them are confident with European grants, research projects and use the very formal academic language, read papers, journals and technical documents on various topics.
- Manufacturers, investors, OEMs and Solution providers of both macro areas of Robotics and Healthcare have been included in a category named *European Companies* (T4). This cluster groups people that can read and use a robotic-related medical terminology and technical jargon but use an informal register. All of these companies have the same interest in results and business opportunities.

1.13.1 Segmentation bases & profile construction

Segmentation bases can be classified into five major categories useful for profile construction; not all of them are necessary or can be defined for each segment:

- Geographic base: segmenting by country, region, city or other geographic details;
- Demographic base: segmenting based on identifiable population characteristics, such as age, occupation, marital status and so on;
- Psychographic base: this segmentation approach involves an understanding of a consumer's lifestyle, interests, and opinions;
- Behavioral base: segmenting the market based on their relationship with the product or the company, if they are heavy/light users, brand loyal or brand switchers, and so on;
- Benefits base: this approach segments consumers because of specific benefits they are seeking from the product, such as convenience, or status, or value, and so on.

1.13.2 General Public (T1) Profile

They are all non-experts interested in the topics of robotics (and healthcare), not involved in the use or the development of them and need the same informal registry and non-technical language.

Consumers in this market segment are mainly European citizens; in particular we will first address our communication to our Partners' local markets (Italy, Spain, UK, Germany and Austria).

We will include:

- Patients
- Voluntary organisations and communities
- Carers
- People that care about living healthier lives

These consumers are healthy people or altruists that care about others; health matters to them because it makes them confident, free and productive. They enjoy interacting with the world, connect and build relationships with others, communicate and express themselves because this establishes their wider purpose in life.

This segment includes also end users that enjoy creating, buying, testing, evaluating and learning about new technology:

- Geeks
- Robotics enthusiasts
- Citizen interested in science
- People fascinated by new technologies
- Tech Media & journalists (Tech Youtubers, Bloggers, Podcasters, Vloggers..)

Technology is everything they talk about, their primary concern is what is new and what works better, when they are on the internet all they look for is new technology or new trends in technology. Tech enthusiasts are always learning or discovering new ways to do things better using technology³.

1.13.3 Healthcare Experts (T2) Profile

They are all healthcare experts, involved in the use of robotics for medical purposes and adopt the same formal registry and medical language.

This segment includes:

- Hospitals and Clinical Centers operators
- Surgeons

³Source: <https://www.quora.com/What-does-technology-enthusiast-mean>

- Medical Operators
- Anesthetists
- Nurses
- Clinicians and other staff

1.13.4 Researchers (T3) Profile⁴

They are all familiar with European grants, research projects and use the very formal academic language, read papers, journals and technical documents about different topics.

They are:

- **Researchers from** surgical robotics, computer vision, machine learning
- **Scientific communities** from both the **private and the public sector**

Geographically, Researchers are located both inside and outside Europe. We will pay particular attention to our Partners' local markets (Italy, Spain, UK, Germany and Austria).

1.13.5 European companies (T4) Profile

This cluster groups industrial stakeholders, i.e. potential manufacturers of surgical robotic tools and of specific subsystems (software and hardware). They can read and use a medical terminology and technical jargon on robotics, but use an informal register. All of these companies have the same interest in results and business opportunities.

Business description: they mainly operate in the Medical and/or Robotics Industry, but also in the Professional service robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare technology, Industrial robotics, Software & applications, Internet of things. Some are startups and/or spin-offs.

Geographically, we will be addressing our communication to European Companies, with a particular attention to our Partners' local markets (Italy, Spain, UK, Germany and Austria).

⁴ http://www.infodata.ilsole24ore.com/2017/07/08/ricercatori-quanto-guadagnano-vivono/?refresh_ce=1

1.14 Positioning strategy

The last step in creating market segments concerns the strategy and more specifically the development of a positioning strategy by identifying key benefits and relevant features for segments and building a “product” positioning in line with their perception.

1.14.1 General Public (T1)

A key step in the scientific process is the communication activity, addressed to the general public, of academic notions and research outcomes in an accessible and easily comprehensible form. The effective transmission of information about the project and its results to a wider audience allows us to influence the public perception, raise awareness, build credibility for the scientists involved and increases the value of the project’s scientific findings.

Effective communication can maximize the value of scientific discoveries. However, in order for a scientific message reach an audience composed by non-scientists, it is crucial to consider the language used, adapt one’s tone, manner, and use the right media. Here follows the guidelines we will adopt in our communication plan to spread the message to patients and the general public.

1.14.1.1 Objective

We aim at showing that our system is valuable in terms of costs for welfare, healthcare systems and patients. We will work to increase the acceptability of robotic procedures by communicating to the public and patients the safety and well-being improvements associated with our results.

1.14.1.2 Media mix

- Website
- Press releases (PR) to mainstream media and patient associations
- Social Media: Facebook page/groups, twitter, LinkedIn (Youtube)
- Newsletters published on the SARAS website
- Conferences and events in general are less effective but we will evaluate any event focused on patient associations and scientific divulgation in general

Message guidelines:

- Simplify the messages
- Keep them short
- Avoid scientific jargon
- Don't expect data to speak for you
- Key messages need to be supported by visual evidence
- Talk about people involved, processes, explain how it works in practice and what are the benefits
- Use storytelling techniques
- Use analogies and metaphors

Content type

- Blog news about updates on scientific progresses
- Poster and flyers to update on the results of the project
- Photos with extensive descriptions and captions
- Graphic and visual tools such as diagrams, schemes and infographics
- Demos and videos if feasible

- Likes, shares, retweets of hot topics

1.14.2 Healthcare experts (T2)

1.14.2.1 Objective

SARAS' results will improve surgeon awareness and their trust in autonomous robotic systems. A key objective of SARAS is the proactive nurturing of a generation of surgeons familiar and comfortable with the unprecedented level of autonomy provided by SARAS.

1.14.2.2 Media Mix

Website: project description, medical conferences, workshops and main **publications** (if public) will be listed and/or included

Training activities

European training centers focused on robotic MIS will be contacted in the perspective of future coordination and collaboration, all partners will contribute involving the following centers:

- The clinical partner OSR -a core component of SARAS' engagement with surgeons
- Surgitrainer, a spin-off company of UPC active on surgical trainers
- UNIVR will integrate SARAS' outcomes in the syllabus of the course "Introduction to Robotic Surgery" course within the Master degree in Medicine and Surgery
- The World Robotic Surgery Education (WRSE) event, via the Department of Urology of Verona (UNIVR) - one of the 14 world-leading centers participating
- The Ninewells Hospital via UNIVDUN
- ACMIT will introduce SARAS' outcomes to its network of clinical partners and hospital operators

Publications workshops, special sessions in conferences and **articles in journals** in the medical and/or robotic field(s) at the discretion of the partners.

Events

- **A workshop at OSR** at the end of the project, to showcase SARAS' results in a practical way and increase the interest of hospitals and healthcare centers for further exploitation. Such event will involve the participation of different hospital representatives, invited by all Partners.
- **Medical conferences** in the medical and/or robotic field(s) at the discretion of the partners.
- The SARAS dedicated **workshops** to inform clinical staff

News updates

- On the web site news area
- Through national association's mailing lists (ei. ALSbig), if provided.

Content type

Arguments to improve Surgeons trust in autonomous systems can be the demonstration of a measurable reduction of errors, the fact that the interface can be personalized by each individual surgeon, and that the multimodal interface will guide surgeons throughout the training phase.

1.14.3 Researchers (T3)

1.14.3.1 Objective

To engage and encourage participation in research, to educate and inspire the next generation of scientists in order to expand the European network of researchers in the field of cognitive robotics and autonomous robots.

1.14.3.2 Media Mix

Website: scientific events and main publications (if public) will be listed and/or included
Publications workshops, special sessions in conferences and articles in journals in Robotics, Computer Vision, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence at the discretion of the partners.

Workshops: two workshops will be organized, during year 2 and year 3 of the project to summarize results, present achievements obtained, demos, and outline the desired targets for the next period. Participants and speakers will be researchers in robotics and surgery.

Summer school: COSUR2018 (Verona, Italy) to introduce PhD students and Post-Doctoral fellows to the multidisciplinary research field of surgical robotics. The school will offer lectures, hands-on laboratory experience and opportunity for informal interaction with clinicians and leading experts from academia and industry. The final goal is the creation of a new generation of researchers with skills in surgical robotics.

For more details: <http://metropolis.scienze.univr.it/altair/events/summer-school-on-control-of-surgical-robots-cosur-2018/>

Topics

Young researchers are extremely interested in artificial intelligence, deep learning and cognition, fully autonomous systems, and human-robot collaboration. Such exciting perspectives will excite them, and they will enjoy expanded professional opportunities as a result.

1.14.4 European Companies (T4)

1.14.4.1 Objective

To open new markets in the European industrial world of surgical robotics, phantoms design and training, thanks to the enormous potential for SARAS-like systems in Europe.

SARAS pushes human-robot cooperation to a new level and it focusses on one of the key technologies of the Industry 4.0 program.

1.14.4.2 Media Mix

Website

Social Media

PR & News

Exhibitions trade fairs and demos of SARAS outcomes are foreseen at the main events in the field.

Technology transfer center: SARAS' non-academic partners (MEDIN and ACMIT), will exploit their network to disseminate commercially the results of the project, with the aim of expanding the network of companies interested in the project's outcomes.

Workshops with the industrial players to spread the knowledge of SARAS' cooperative technologies. The connection of UNIMORE, UNIFE and UNIVR have links with local and regional industrial associations, which will allow contacting a number of companies interested in cooperative robotics.

Networking & inbound marketing focuses on relationships with prospective customers and it relies heavily on building networks with them. The aim of inbound is to create content, which appeals to customers, and content that triggers the target to interact with the content. Different methods of inbound marketing include e-books, newsletters and blogs. Inbound marketing is generally time-consuming, and requires great attention to the quality of the message. For all those reasons, the Innovation & Dissemination Manager (IDM) will publish only contents coming from the partners.

	General Public (T1)	Healthcare Experts (T2)	Researchers (T3)	European companies (T4)
Website				
Press releases				
Social Media				
Facebook				
Twitter				
LinkedIn				
Youtube				
Newsletters				
EVENTS				
Exhibitions/tradefair				
Final demonstration				
Conferences				
Workshops				
TRAININGS				
PAPERS/JOURNALS				

Table 2: Sum up of the Media Mix adopted for each target audience

Communication Plan

A communication plan is a roadmap with all communication activities identified as necessary and useful in the strategy to better deliver the right messages to the right target audiences. SARAS' consortium is strongly committed to communicating and promoting project activities and outcomes to all the stakeholders, as their involvement is essential to the success of the project. Our communication plan will be carried out throughout the project's entire lifespan (36 months).

1.15 Communication activities description

1.15.1 Press Releases

PR are the most important means of communication used in dissemination because of their focus on achievements, milestones, developments and results. Press releases will be produced throughout the project's duration in correspondence with specific achieved goals in order to engage audiences. Each partner must contribute by submitting ideas and providing suggestions on topics, and should contribute by translating releases into their local language and distributing them via their press offices. Each PR will be published on the website in the News area and distributed by the partner's press offices (where present) to a list of recommended online and printed magazines.

1.15.2 Content: Curation & marketing

Content is king in communication; to attract interest and retain the audience's attention we must produce relevant contents and release them through the appropriate means of communication to the right audience. Content is generated by (i) content curation and (ii) content marketing.

1.15.2.1 Content Curation

Content curation is the process of sharing the most informative and interesting pieces from other sources, social accounts and blogs of the industry/sector around specific keywords, topics, domains, etc. The main objective of Content Curation is to (i) build brand awareness, (ii) gain brand exposure by adding a perspective to quality content of relevant sources of the sector; (iii) improve SEO (Search Engine Optimization) creating additional doorways into SARAS' site through indexable pages, back links; (iiii) increase engagement with the relevant audience.

The content curation process consist of:

- Screening and finding the most shared and talked about stories in the industry
- Finding top sources to link to
- Compiling a list of sources
- Reading and collecting relevant news
- Buffering them on SARAS' social media

To this extent, the IDM will ask all partners to list the top source for their specific sector.

1.15.2.2 Content Marketing

Content Marketing denotes the creation and distribution of valuable and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined audience. The key is to provide truly relevant and useful content to audiences, best if useful to them to solve issues or meet their needs. Whereas SARAS' Researchers will produce papers for the respective academic audiences, the IDM will write, with the help of all Partners, contents for the general public, the healthcare experts and European companies.

Because of the complexity of the topic and the very specific use of SARAS' robotic arms, marketing contents produced will be maximized, reused and adapted to extend their lifetime. This involves:

- Converting existing content into other formats, e.g. by making a visual version (infographic) of an article
- Repurposing existing information into a new piece of content, (e.g., by dividing big content into smaller chunks and collating smaller pieces of information into a longer format)
-
- Collecting blog posts on a given topic into a training or resource section
- Writing FAQs or glossaries
- Publishing partners' interviews and bios enriched with storytelling techniques

The IDM will send out questionnaires for project leaders to describe their Work package, their objectives, the methodology, expected results, and obtain enough information to write press releases, web highlight and social posts. The idea is to collect all partners' information by the end of the project and give every partner the same level of visibility. Everyone's collaboration is necessary for the success of the task.

1.15.3 Website

The Website is the place where to showcase the entire project and it is the place where all other media must convey traffic. The main purpose of a project website is to facilitate the communication, dissemination and exploitation of outcomes, to extend the project's network and to communicate scientific results.

SARAS' website presents information targeting different audiences; it provides to stakeholders information about the project, its actors, its objectives to stakeholders; it is constantly updated with the project's status, its outcomes and achievements. Visitors have access to all information about the project, they can download promotional material, press releases and public deliverables. The website has a responsive design which makes web pages render well on a variety of devices and window or screen sizes and it should display equally well from widescreen monitors to mobile phones. The website is now up-to-date with events, publications, results and news arisen so far and it will be regularly updated within the 36 months of the project duration.

The official website of the project is available at the following address: <https://saras-project.eu/>

1.15.3.1 Structure

The structure and navigation of the website is operational and articulated around the following main sections:

- *Home*: the home page of the web site (see **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**);
- *Project*: provides a general overview of the project, in terms of objectives, concept and approach, ambition and impact;
- *Consortium*: lists all partners involved in the project, their roles and the management structure, including the work plan and work packages objectives;
- *Downloads*: the area where to find all project's outputs, such as brochure, public deliverables, guidelines and so on;
- *News*: a blog area with all news, press releases and announcements about the project;

- **Events:** a calendar and a list of all events Partners’ have attended and will attend. Each event has also a dedicated single page where visitors can obtain all information included venue and date, view the gallery and download presentations (if available);
- **Contact:** details on how to reach the project coordinator.

Figure 15: Home Page of SARAS’ website

1.15.3.2 Contents

To connect our audiences to SARAS we are going to create high quality content, launch strong PR and social campaigns and build a quality website meant for users. We are going to create linkable assets,

such as white papers, videos, podcasts, brochures, webinars and other educational resources, which can be disseminated through social, PR and blog programs to reach relevant audiences. The News area serves as a centerpiece for housing thought leadership and other assets and make results appealing to people.

SEO

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is an organic marketing strategy that uses different optimization tactics (such as creating organic links with others and improving social media presence) to improve the project’s website ranking on Google search engine. The aim is to guarantee that the project is among the top of the lists when stakeholders are searching for relevant keywords. Search engine marketing can guarantee the project a better online visibility and it can be relatively cost effective.

Plugins

- To manage all aspects of the cookie and privacy and comply with European privacy regulations (GDPR) we used:
 - **EU Cookies Law plugin** to create the Cookie Banner (see Figure 16: Cookie Banner)
 - Cookiebot www.cookiebot.com to write a compliant banner text
 - Iubenda <https://www.iubenda.com/en/help/posts/1215> to write the Privacy Policy
- **Addthis** is a plug in that allow us to spread our messages all over the internet thanks to ‘share’ and ‘follow’ buttons. We have added a Header bar with follow buttons on social media and a Floating bar with share buttons (see Figure 17).
- **Easy Twitter Feed Widget Plugin** to add SARAS’ twitter feeds on the web site
- **The Events Calendar** is a carefully crafted, extensible plugin that allows easily sharing events.

Figure 16: Cookie Banner

Figure 17: Follow buttons (top right) and Floating bar with share buttons (left)

are in fact intensely visual and ephemeral, the user base is aged 13-29 and they are channels mainly used for telling short visual stories or make an impression.

We have created and configured a Buffer account (<https://buffer.com/>) to manage all of SARAS' social media accounts from one simple dashboard and make it simple to schedule posts, analyze performance, track engagement and interactions on the posts shared. To avoid any loss of data, and to keep the Buffer profile easily accessible and fully secure the registration was done using SARAS' Twitter account and the Google account InnovationDisseminationHSR@gmail.com⁶.

Figure 19: SARAS Social Media Cover

1.15.4.1 Facebook

Facebook is the social media for everything. It is part of our lives, over 2 billion people use it every month and it is personal. It is ideal to communicate mainly with young people, millennials (18-29 years old) and generation X (30-49), though also elder people are quite active and younger users are migrating to newer platforms. The type of content that works better on Facebook are contests and stories in which customers/users are the heroes. The tone must be conversational and casual. The main reason to use it is to engage a dialogue with followers.

Profile page url: <https://www.facebook.com/SarasH2020/>

1.15.4.2 Twitter

Twitter is the social media for people and companies that have something interesting to say. It enlists 317 million of monthly active users. It is completely public, so that everyone can start following the SARAS page and get in contact; replying is mandatory to keep followers engaged. It is ideal to communicate the results of a research, share resources, promote events and publications, build online communities, connect with people and communicate with followers. 65% of users are under the age of 34. It is mainly exploited to expand one's audience using links to valuable content and requires time to engage with users. Content must include a personal comment, the visual must be eye-catching and the tone must be friendly, simple and informal regardless the audience. Brevity is

⁶ Do not use this email account for internal communication – it is only for social media management.

the rule and content's longevity is measured in minutes or hours. Ideally, one should post twice a day, but the reality is that one should only post when they have something to say. To make the most out of Twitter and know when is the best moment of the day and the day of the week to post, we have installed a free twitter tool called *Tweriod* that analyses followers' online presence and lets us know the best time to tweet.

Profile page url: <https://twitter.com/SarasH2020>

Topics

- News
- Events
- Publications
- Resources available on the web
- Media: video, demo, photos, link of presentations on slide share and podcasts
- Questions, polls, survey links

Hashtags

Hashtags “#” are keyword assigned to words or phrases that allow them to be found by searching on social media. Hashtags help stand out amongst the crowd, index contents, become accessible to all users interested in similar topics even when not followers or fans. Using two or three of them in each tweet guarantees an increase of 20% in terms of audience size. SARAS suggested hashtags are: #Research #Robotics #EuRobotics #healthcare #eurobotics #EuResearch #MedicalRobotics #Surgicalrobotics #RoboticSurgery #h2020 [@SarasH2020](https://twitter.com/SarasH2020)

Lists

A list is a curated group of Twitter accounts, used to organize connections, to easily listen to their tweets or just to know who is who. Because of multiple audience segments we are targeting in our communication plan, we created different lists to reach different segments:

- GeneralPublic
- Industry&companies
- Media&trends is a list with Journalist, bloggers, writers, editors we assume being influencers on tech news, with a particular interest in robotics
- ResearchAcademia: European Commission, research results, educational, university
- SARASpartners
- Surgeons_Hopitals

1.15.4.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the world's largest professional social media network, connecting 106 million of people⁷ and helping develop their careers. The majority of LinkedIn users are over 30, have a higher education degree and a senior-level job position (influencers, decision makers, and C-level executives). The content that performs best on LinkedIn is content that helps being more efficient or industry-specific content. Ideal for salespeople to connect with prospects and for marketers to run Lead generation campaigns. LinkedIn is a little more formal than the other channels, but just in terms of contents (no kittens or vacation photos); the tone must be professional but never impersonal. By posing questions, publishing useful content and answering others' questions, the project can develop a following and build up an expertise status. LinkedIn Groups are especially useful for this purpose.

⁷ <http://www.viraleffect.com/blog/linkedin-in-the-professional-social-network/>

Profile page to be activated soon.

1.15.5 Events

There are various types of events depending on audiences, objectives, budget and topics; for these reasons the IDM will collect all Partners event lists and communicate the participation through all relevant channels, included a dedicated web page with collateral publication (where provided).

- **Exhibitions and trade fair** are business events particularly relevant for the industry related topics; there companies showcase new products, technologies or present services.
- **Conferences** are the best way to meet peers in person, they can help gaining connections and nurture collaborations; popular in the academic and medical fields.
- **Workshops and Seminars** are informative/educational events for the demonstration of a product and/or the training of attendees.

See **Errorre. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** for a draft list that will be regularly updated during the 36 months of the project's duration.

1.16 Action plan

The Communication Plan in addition to the strategy, which is the general plan of what the Consortium intends to do for a certain target in the long term (3 years), includes the Action plan: a sequence of phases and the time needed to implement them in the short term (12 months).

1.16.1 Event calendar

Here a draft list of events that Partners have shown some interest in and/or that they probably would like to attend. This list will be updated during the entire duration of the project and published in the Dissemination plan together with results. The IDM will submit to partners other events of possible interest and all Partners will communicate in advance their event plan to allow the IDM to update the event page on the website, create dedicate pages and communicate the participation through the means of communication the IDM will consider appropriated.

Event Category	#month	Year	Target Audience	Macroarea	Event NAME	VENUE
Conference	M2	2018	T2	Surgery	SIC 2018 - Primo Convegno delle Società Chirurgiche della Campania, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria Sicilia.	Naples, Italy
Fair (expo+conf)	M3	2018	T3/T4	Robotics	ERF2018 -The European Robotics Forum (ERF2018)	Tampere, Finland
Conference	M5	2018	T3	Robotics	ICRA2018 - IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation	Brisbane, Australia
Conference	M5	2018	T2	Surgical training	AEDV 2018 46 th National Conference on Dermatology and Veneorology	Mallorca (Spain)
Workshop	M6	2018	T2	Surgical training	2 MelaTx Workshop	Sevilla (Spain)
Fair (expo+conf)	M6	2018	T3	computer vision	CVPR 2018- Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition	Salt Lake City, Utah

Exhibitions	M6	2018	T4	Robotics	AUTOMATICA 2018	Munich, Germany
Exhibitions	M7	2018	T4	medical technology	EndoBarcelona	Barcelona, Spain
Conference	M9	2018	T3	computer vision	ECCV2018 - European Conference on Computer Vision	Munich, Germany
Workshop	M9	2018	T3	Surgery Robots	CRAS2018 - Computer/Robot Assisted Surgery	London, United Kingdom
Conference	M10	2018	T3	Robotics	IROS2018/ IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)	Madrid, Spain
Exhibitions	M11	2018	T4	medical technology	MEDICA 2018	Düsseldorf - Germany
Conference	M12	2018	T3	machine learning	NIPS2018 - Neural Information Processing Systems	Montréal, CANADA
Fair (expo+conf)	M15	2019	T3/T4	Robotics	ERF2019 - The European Robotics Forum	TBD
Conference	M17	2019	T3	Robotics	ICRA IEEE Conference on Robotics and Automation	Montreal/ Canada

Table 3: Short-term event calendar (12 months)

The Consortium is planning to organize a number of workshops to update and involve the different target audiences on different topics and held a Demonstration at the very end of the project. Formula, dates and locations will be confirmed/defined during the next 12 months.

Event Category	# month	Year	Target Audience	Event NAME
Surgical Training	M6	2018	T2	2 MelaTx Workshop
Workshop	M18	2019	T2	SARAS Workshop for clinical staff
Workshop	M22	2019	T3	SARAS Workshop Y2 - results - achievements - targets
Workshop	M30	2020	T4	SARAS Workshop with Industrial Players
Workshop	M34	2020	T3	SARAS Workshop Y3 - results - achievements - targets
Demo	M36	2020	T2	SARAS Final demonstration of the SARAS system in OSR

Table 4: Consortium Demo and Workshops

1.16.2 Editorial calendar

Consortium Review Meetings, Milestones and public Deliverables will be used as inspirational topics for the editorial calendar if considered relevant for the target audiences; in some cases they will be communicated or published via the proper means of communication (on the website, social media or press release). During the project’s lifespan, the IDM will also share with Partners questionnaires and news that will help to write pieces highlighting specific aspects, curiosities or tell the story of prominent personalities in the Consortium with the sole aim of involving the public. Here follows the list of inspirational deadlines. The complete and definitive editorial calendar together with SARAS’ results will be updated in the Dissemination calendar.

D8.1 – PLAN FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

Output Category	#month	Year	Output name
Review Meeting	M1	2018	Kick-off meeting
Deliverable	M6	2018	D1.1 Requirements for surgical actions
Deliverable	M6	2018	D8.1 Plan for Communication actions
Deliverable	M6	2018	D9.6 Data Management Plan
Milestone	M6	2018	MS2 Surgical and Technical specifications
Review Meeting	M9	2018	Project meeting & Remote Review Meeting
Deliverable	M12	2018	D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTSSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M12	2018	D2.1 Patient specific based phantom models
Deliverable	M12	2018	D3.1 Multi-modal human-robot interfaces and architecture for the MULTIROBOTSSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M12	2018	D4.1 Tasks mapping
Deliverable	M12	2018	D7.2 Software/Hardware architecture for the MULTIROBOTSSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M12	2018	D8.2 Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (Y1)
Milestone	M12	2018	MS3 Phantom models
Milestone	M12	2018	MS4 MULTIROBOTSSURGERY
Review Meeting	M12	2018	Integration week for MULTI-ROBOT SURGERY platform (+ video)
Review Meeting	M15	2019	Project meeting
Deliverable	M18	2019	D5.1 3D modelling of anatomy and 3D registration
Deliverable	M18	2019	D6.1 Real-time surgeon action detection and recognition
Review Meeting	M21	2019	Mid-term review meeting
Deliverable	M24	2019	D1.3 Experimental tests and validation activities on the SOLOSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M24	2019	D2.2 Advanced phantom models
Deliverable	M24	2019	D3.2 Multi-modal human-robot interfaces and architecture for the SOLO-SURGERY platform
Deliverable	M24	2019	D4.2 Algorithms for robot motion planning in dynamic environments
Deliverable	M24	2019	D4.3 Multi-Robot Cooperation Platform for the SOLOSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M24	2019	D5.2 Labelling and segmentation tool
Deliverable	M24	2019	D5.3 Cognitive control for the SOLOSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M24	2019	D6.2 Prediction of future surgeon actions and decision-making policy for the SOLOSURGERY system
Deliverable	M24	2019	D7.3 Software/Hardware architecture for the SOLOSURGERY platform
Deliverable	M24	2019	D8.3 Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (Y2)
Milestone	M24	2019	MS5 Advanced phantom
Milestone	M24	2019	MS6 SOLO-SURGERY
Milestone	M24	2019	MS7 Dissemination II
Review Meeting	M24	2019	Integration week for SOLO SURGERY platform (+ video)
Review Meeting	M27	2020	Project meeting
Deliverable	M30	2020	D5.4 Tracking of robot arms and deformable organs and tissue
Deliverable	M36	2020	D1.4 Experimental tests and validation activities on the LAPARO2.0- SURGERY platform

Deliverable	M36	2020	D2.3 Thiel soft embalmed human cadaver model
Deliverable	M36	2020	D3.3 Humanrobot interfaces for the LAPARO2.0- SURGERY platform
Deliverable	M36	2020	D4.4 Implementation and verification of motion planning system
Deliverable	M36	2020	D4.5 Multi-Robot Cooperation Platform for the LAPARO2.0- SURGERY platform
Deliverable	M36	2020	D5.5 Cognitive control for the LAPARO2.0-SURGERY platform
Deliverable	M36	2020	D6.3 Prediction of future surgeon actions and decision making for LAPARO2.0-SURGERY
Deliverable	M36	2020	D7.4 Software/ Hardware architecture for the LAPARO2.0-SURGERY platform
Deliverable	M36	2020	D8.4 Business Analysis
Deliverable	M36	2020	D8.5 Report on legal issues and certification procedures
Milestone	M36	2020	MS8 Thiel soft embalmed human cadaver
Milestone	M36	2020	MS9 LAPARO2.0-SURGERY
Milestone	M36	2020	MS10 Dissemination III and Exploitation
Review Meeting	M36	2020	Integration week for LAPARO SURGERY platform (+ video)
Review Meeting	M38	2021	Final Review meeting (with video of SOLO SURGERY platform)

Table 5: Output calendar for editorial opportunities

Appendix

Annex